

COMPARISON BETWEEN GLASS AND FLAX NON-CRIMP STITCHED FABRICS

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1 Introduction

A lot of work has been devoted recently on the study of plant fiber composites, especially with short fibers. Different trials have been attempted with different fibers (hemp, flax, kenaf, jute, etc.) and different matrices (polypropylene, polylactic acid, polyester, epoxy, etc.). Increasing compatibility between these lignocellulosic fibers and thermoplastics or thermosetting matrices has been the object of various studies.

Investigations treating the subject of plant fiber composites usually deal with compounds processing. In other studies, randomly ordered fiber mats are used. More recently short fiber injection has also been investigated [1].

To increase the mechanical performance of plant fiber composites, it seems of interest to study composites elaborated with aligned fiber reinforcements that can be preplaced in a mould and injected as in Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) processes. A previous and promising work of Oksman [2] showed flax fiber composites elaborated by RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) with very good mechanical properties. Especially flax-epoxy UD composites gave a Young's modulus of 40 GPa. Therefore it is relevant to study LCM processing parameters of plant fiber composites in order to optimize them. Recently, Rassmann *and al.* showed that drying of kenaf fibers - arranged in non-woven mats - before injection in a RTM mold by polyester resin do not have any effect on mechanical properties [3].

Investigations on plant fiber composites usually do not detail the exact arrangement of the fibers and its effect on composite properties. As an exception, Liu and Hughes test mechanically different flax woven fabrics with an epoxy matrix but conclude that the

influence of the weave type was not significant on fracture behavior and toughness of the composites [4].

Our study compares glass and flax fibers arranged in non-crimp stitched fabrics. This paper gives results on critical process parameters, i.e. longitudinal and transverse permeability, for both non-crimped fabrics. Tensile mechanical properties from these non-crimped fabrics associated with a classical epoxy resin and a partially agro-resourced polyurethane are also presented.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Fabrics

Flax and glass fabrics are Non-Crimp Fabrics (NCF) and possess the same areal weight (around 500g.m⁻²). They both consist in two perpendicular layers of unidirectional fibers joined together by a stitching at 45° of the two layers.

Both fabrics are elaborated with the same machine. The layers inside fabrics are formed without yarns so fibers are really straight along the direction of one layer.

NCF is an interesting structure to prospect in the case of flax fiber composites because it allows higher volume fractions of fibers than other structures like random or woven mats.

2.2 Permeability measurements

Permeability is measured in two principal directions: in the plane along the fibers, i.e. longitudinal permeability and out of plane, i.e. transverse permeability. Permeability is measured in both cases with silicon oil, Rhodorsil 47V100, whose viscosity is around 0.1 Pa.s at ambient temperature.

Evolutions of longitudinal and transverse permeabilities are given as a function of the volume fraction of fibers.

Longitudinal permeability is measured inside a dedicated permeability measurement device (Fig. 1) with a constant pressure difference (1.0 bar). A preform is placed in a rectangular cavity with a length of 50 cm, a width of 10 cm and a thickness of 3.85 mm. According to the volume fraction of fibers to obtain, number of plies is varied (2, 3 and 4 for flax and 4, 6 and 8 for glass fabrics). Unsaturated permeability is determined from impregnation of the preform visualized through a glass window placed on the upper side of the cavity (Fig. 1a). Saturated permeability is given by weighing of the liquid flowing out the filled cavity. Set-up and methods used are more described in Re et al. [5].

Transverse permeability is measured only in saturated condition with the “classical” method described in Ouagne and Bréard [6] and the set-up shown on Fig. 2. The “classical” method consists in measuring the difference of pressure given by a constant flow rate on a 100mm diameter stack of plies. In one experiment, the same stack is more or less compressed at different steps to obtain different volume fractions of fibers.

Darcy’s law is used in transverse and longitudinal permeability determination from measurements.

2.3 Tensile properties measurements

Matrices used are an epoxy resin (SR8100) and a polyurethane partially agro-resourced resin (MD 1787). Details are available in table 1. Some mechanical properties of the pure resins as given in manufacturer’s datasheets are reported in table 2. Composites were elaborated by compression at a temperature of 60°C and post-cured according to manufacturer (Table 1). The same number of plies is used for flax or glass reinforcements. Tensile tests are done as according to ISO 527 over three samples for each composite.

3 Results

3.1 Permeability results

Longitudinal permeability (Fig. 3) shows lower values for flax than glass in both unsaturated and saturated conditions whereas transverse permeability (Fig. 4) is quite similar for both types of fibers. For

example, longitudinal saturated permeability is between four and six times lower for flax than glass preforms at the same volume fraction of fibers in the range of the measurements. In other words, flax is harder to impregnate than glass parallel to the fabrics.

The identical transverse permeability for glass and flax preforms seems in agreement with a previous result of Drapier *and al.* [7] which specifies that transverse permeability of a non-crimped new concept (NC2) biaxial reinforcement increases linearly with the stitching density of the fabrics. Our flax and glass fabrics are elaborated in the same way. So they possess the same characteristics of stitching. Then it seems logical to observe comparable permeability values despite the change in nature of fibers. This only works if one considers the pores around the stitches globally responsible for the flow through the fabrics.

For the flax fabrics studied and by comparison with glass ones, LCM processes promoting transverse injections, such as infusion, should be preferred to the ones related to longitudinal permeability, as RTM for example. It also may be possible to improve flax fabrics by enhancing longitudinal permeability.

3.2 Tensile mechanical properties

Flax composites give lower Young’s modulus (around 2/3) and lower tensile strength (between 40 and 50%) than glass ones (Figs 5 and 6). Strain at failure (Fig. 7) is consequently 60% higher for glass composites. Flax/Bioresin composites show slight higher rigidity than Flax/Epoxy ones (Fig. 5).

Specific mechanical properties of the different composites, i.e. Young’s modulus and tensile strength divided by composite density, are reported on figures 7 and 8. It is observed that specific rigidity is similar for the different combinations of constituents at a constant volume fraction of fibers whereas specific strength remains lower for flax composites than glass ones. At high volume fraction of fibers, flax/Bioresin composites even tend to have higher specific modulus than glass/Epoxy ones (Fig. 7). This can be explained simultaneously by the higher stiffness of the Bioresin (Tab. 2) and the lower density of flax fibers.

4 Conclusions

Studied flax NCF is more difficult to impregnate than similar glass NCF in a longitudinal way. Transverse impregnation is similar in glass and flax fabrics. Infusion processes should then be preferred to RTM injection for this flax NCF. Flax composites give lower tensile properties, especially tensile strength, than glass ones. However flax composite tensile properties are sufficient for various structural applications. In particular, flax-polyurethane composites containing a high agro-resourced content are competitive in term of specific stiffness.

Name	Supplier	Agro-resourced fraction (wt %)	Post-cure time / temperature
SR 8100	Sicomini	0.0	8h / 60°C
Catalyst SD 8824			
Biothan MD 1787	Bioresin /Sandtech	49.5	2h / 80°C
Catalyst M330			

Tab.1. Thermosetting matrices used.

Name	Modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain at failure (%)
SR 8100	2.4	59	5.9
Catalyst SD 8824			
Biothan MD 1787	> 3.0	-	6.4
Catalyst M330			

Tab.2. Mechanical properties of the resins.

Fig.1. Longitudinal permeability measurement setup: a) view above the closed mould during an experiment; b) view of the opened and empty mould.

Fig.2. Transverse permeability measurement setup (open) [6].

Fig.3. Longitudinal permeability values for glass and flax performs as a function of fiber volume fraction.

Fig.4. Transverse permeability values for glass and flax performs as a function of fiber volume fraction.

Fig.5. Young's modulus for the prepared composites.

Fig.6. Tensile strength for the prepared composites.

Fig.7. Strain at failure for the prepared composites.

Fig.8. Specific Young's modulus values.

Fig.9. Specific tensile strength values.

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